

**COLLEGES OF SHRI SHIVAJI EDUCATION SOCIETY,
AMRAVATI AND THEIR TEAM ACHIEVEMENT IN THE
UNIVERSITIES OF THE VIDARBHA REGION**

Devendra Chandrasen Wankhade

Department of Physical Education and Sports, Dhanwate National College,
Nagpur, Maharashtra

Cite This Article: Devendra Chandrasen Wankhade, “Colleges of Shri Shivaji Education Society, Amravati and Their Team Achievement in the Universities of the Vidarbha Region”, International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education, Volume 6, Issue 1, Page Number 30-33, 2020.

Copy Right: © IJMRME, 2020 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

Physical education and sports are considered to be the most important factors in developing personality. The objective of physical education is to develop a person through physical activities. Keeping this objective in mind and working in the college of the Society, The study has been completed on the purpose of seeing “The Contribution of Shri Shivaji Education Society, Amravati in the field of Physical Education & Sports. Shri Shivaji Education Society is the largest educational institution in Vidarbha. It provides education in 28 colleges in total, including arts, commerce, science, law, agriculture, education, physical education, management, engineering, medical, drawing, etc. These colleges are affiliated to Sant Gadgebaba Amravati University, Amravati, Rashtrasant Tukadoji Maharaj Nagpur University, Nagpur, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krushi Vidyapeeth, Akola, Health Sciences University, Nashik and Mumbai Technical Board. The data are compiled through questionnaires and annual reports of the university and institution to complete this study. Studying about 10 main areas, they analyzed the team titles and the proportion of the university affiliated colleges in various inter-college competitions organized by the Universities. The study has revealed some important findings, which are more than double the number of Championship and subtitles, mainly compared to the college number of the organization. It has been concluded that the winning percentage of society’s Colleges at 12.69%, 7.55% & 19.05% and the percentage of runners-up 12.82%, 4.53%, 20.00% respectively Sant Gadgebaba Amravati University, Rashtrasant Tukadoji Maharaj Nagpur University and Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krushi Vidyapeeth. In the inter-collegiate tournament team achievements is much higher than the ratio of Shri Shivaji Education Society’s colleges to total number of colleges. This means that the overall progress of the colleges of Shri Shivaji Educational Institution is determined to be successful in the field of physical education.

Key Words: Education Society, Colleges, Universities, Sports, Competitions, Facilities & Achievements

Preface:

Shri Shivaji Education Society, Amravati is a high class educational institution in Vidarbha. Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh founded Shri Shivaji Education Society at Amravati on 1st July 1932. Shri Shivaji Education Society runs 287 institutions (schools, hostels etc. including 28 colleges). After the completion of 12 years of work in the Department of Physical Education & sports of Dhanwate National College, Nagpur. Researcher thought that he should study the contribution of the Shri Shivaji Education Society, Amravati’s in the field of physical education and sports to see what the other college of the institute is going to do in this field. Researcher started work with this aim and received a Ph.D degree in the Faculty of Physical Education by the RTMN University, Nagpur. Physical education and sports are considered to be the most important factors in developing personality.

The objective of physical education is to develop a person through physical activities. According to the national educational policy, the subject of health and physical education is as important as other subjects in education. Physical education is not only about personal health but also about creating society and nation. Also sports is a regular game, a rule of law and a good environment, which develops a person’s physical, mental, intellectual development and quick decision making ability to entertain. Today, the great progress in sports is evident from the grand events of the Olympics, the World Cup, the Asian and Commonwealth Games. The medal tally shows that countries that are at the forefront of the tournament have made progress in all fields. On this basis, what is the physical education and sports related to the colleges run by Shri Shivaji Education Society?

In order to avoid repetition of the topic and get the proper information of the works done in the field has been studied and the details have been presented in the second chapter of the study. Reviews in connection with the topic have also been considered and referred for this study. These reviews are broadly divided under four heads: reviews related to the contribution of physical education & sports, reviews related to the contribution

in education, reviews showing the contribution of Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh in the field physical Education and review giving information about the facilities available for the physical education in various institutions.

The survey method was used by determining the methodology of research. Since the scope of research was limited to senior colleges, the available sample method was used. While receiving the information required for research, the questionnaire is used under primary instruments and annual reports of the University and the Institution under Secondary Practice. Many aspects were considered for the completion of this study. The study was considered for 10 years from 1099-2000 to 2008-2009, when only the senior colleges of the institute were considered. The questionnaire was created based on the ten key factors needed for the development of physical education and sports. These include the physical education and sports facilities of various colleges of the organization, progress, sports charges, use of government schemes, incentive facilities for sportspersons, participation in the sports and participation of the college and its participation in the sports events, training camps and seminars, association of teachers, awards and other activities. Special care was taken to ensure reliability and straightforwardness while creating the questionnaire.

The collection of information was limited to the college run and the information received from the Department of Physical Education and Sports at Sant Gadgebaba Amravati University, Amravati, R.T.M. Nagpur University Nagpur, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krushi Vidyapeeth Akola, and the information received from the Society's Annual Report. The information was collected through questionnaire by the head of Sports Department and other Physical Education Lecturers of all the senior colleges run by the society to complete the research work. In addition, the 10 year annual report and records of Sant Gadgebaba Amravati University, Amravati, R.T.M. Nagpur University Nagpur and Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krushi Vidyapeeth Akola were compiled and records of the department were mainly recorded in the event, including the total number of Championship, total participation in the inter-college tournament, the university training camp, the total number of players for the inter-university tournament, the coach and manager, etc. The annual report of the University and the society was compiled to look at the total number of students in the college and the university's proportion. After compiling all these information, the tables were prepared in chapter 4 according to various aspects. This led to some important conclusions in Chapter 5 by drawing out statistical analysis and graphs.

The Shri Shivaji Education Society has 28 colleges affiliated to four universities, including art, science, commerce, agriculture, law, education, physical education, engineering, medical education and drawing. Among these, Sant Gadgebaba Amravati University - 20, RTM Nagpur University Nagpur and Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krushi Vidyapeeth. Akola 3-3 and Health Science University, Nashik and Mumbai Technical Board 1-1 are affiliated to the college. The total number of colleges at Amravati, Nagpur and Akola University is chart No. 1 is 7.84%, 0.76%, 15.44% respectively.

Table 1: Showing no. of Total Appellate & Society's Colleges of Universities

S.No	University	University Appellate Total College	Shri Shivaji Education Colleges	University Appellate Others College
1	SGBAU, Amravati	255	20	235
2	RTMNU, Nagpur	396	3	393
3	DPDKV, Akola	14	2	12

Graph 1: Showing the % of Society's Colleges in University

In the case of facilities, the college of the society found that 50% of the colleges had gyms and cricket grounds. Some colleges were found to have table tennis and badminton halls, basketball courts, separate tracks,

football, hockey, handball-Korfball grounds. Volleyball, badminton, chess, cricket and athletics equipment's were available to students in a bunker. 50% of college's table tennis, football, basketball, handball, hockey, korfbal and gymnastics equipment's were found in some colleges. All the colleges of the society have sports department; sports equipment's and sports arenas. Besides, the costumes and shoes are given to the sportspersons, while the talented athletes are given a truck suit. 75% of college admissions were prioritised to the players.

The first of our introductions is that only countries that have developed globally are medal-winning in competitions like the Olympics, Asian and Commonwealth. The most important factor in the connection with our organization was the participation of the university competition and the success of the colleges in that competition. The average annual participation of the society's college in the competition organized by all three universities is 16%, the average annual rate of Sant Tukadoji Maharaj Nagpur University is 2.79% and the average annual rate of Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krushi University is 34.55%. In addition, the college was found to be the leader in organizing inter-class competitions in the college.

For this purpose, the sixth area of the questionnaire was given to the team and personal achievement of the colleges run by the Shri Shivaji Education Society. The period of information is 1999-2000 to 2008-2009. It was mainly compiled in first of sixth area of questionnaire and the university had compiled information on the Championship, the sub-titles, the third and fourth positions of the society's colleges in the last ten years. Table No. 2 contains information and analysis of the ten year university declaration and the Championship selections of the society's college. So chart No. 3 analysis of the university declared sub-titles and the success of the colleges of Shri Shivaji Education Society.

Table 2: 10 Year University Declared and Awarded to College of the Society's

S.No	Universities	The total number of championship declared by universities	Number of championships received to other colleges	The number of champions received by the colleges run by the SSES's
1	SGBA University	386	337	49
2	RTMN University	331	306	25
3	DPDK Vidyapeeth	126	101	25

Graph 2: A graph showing the team championship ratio of the colleges declared and run by the University

Table 2 analysing the team title awarded to the society's colleges in the Inter-Collegiate Competition of the University, it is found that the winning percentage of the society's colleges at the Sant Gadgebaba Amravati University is 12.69% and the college number is 7.84%, which is higher than the college number. Similarly, the winning percentage of the society's colleges at the Rashtrasant Tukadoji Maharaj Nagpur University is 7.55% when the college number is only 0.76%. So the winning percentage of the society's colleges at Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krushi Vidyapeeth was proved to be 19.05% is more than 14.28%.

Table 3: 10 Year University Declared and awarded to college of the society

S.No	Universities	The total number of runners-up declared by universities	Number of runners-up received to other colleges	The number of runners-up received by the colleges run by the SSES's
1	SGBA University	343	299	44
2	RTMN University	331	316	15
3	DPDK Vidyapeeth	126	100	26

Graph no. 3: Showing the % of runners-up teams in Universities

Table 3: Is the colleges of the society's has been informed of the team's sub-title in the inter-collegiate competition of the University. In this analysis, Sant Gadgebaba Amravati University, Amravati, Rashtrasant Tukadoji Maharaj Nagpur University, Nagpur and Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krushi Vidyapeeth, Akola is declared by and the sub-title awarded to the Society's colleges is 12.82%, 4.53% and 20.00% respectively. Table no. one shows the number and percentage of the university and the colleges of the society in that university. The percentage of colleges run by Shri Shivaji Education Society is 7.84%, 0.76 % and 14.28% respectively Sant Gadgebaba Amravati University, Rashtrasant Tukadoji Maharaj Nagpur University and Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krushi Vidyapeeth. In relation to the number of champions and runners-up and the number of colleges, the percentage of winners and runners-up is much higher than the number of colleges of Shri Shivaji Education society.

Conclusion:

Shri Shivaji Education Society provides education in arts, commerce, science, law, agriculture, education, physical education, management, engineering, medical, drawing etc. These colleges are mainly affiliated to three universities in Vidarbha region. The performance of the inter-collegiate competition organized by various universities is remarkable as the physical education and sports sector has all the facilities required. The percentage of team championship and university affiliated colleges in the inter-collegiate competition of the institute is more than twice as high as the number of colleges. It has been concluded that the winning percentage of society's Colleges is 12.69%, 7.55 % & 19.05 % and the percentage of runners-up 12.82 %, 4.53 %, 20.00% respectively Sant Gadgebaba Amravati University, Rashtrasant Tukadoji Maharaj Nagpur University and Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krushi Vidyapeeth. In the inter-collegiate tournament team achievements is much higher than the ratio of Shri Shivaji Education Society's colleges to total number of colleges and this means that Shri Shivaji Education Society's colleges are performing excellent and has been creating very good players in the field of sports. This means that the overall progress of the colleges of Shri Shivaji Educational Institution is determined to be successful in the field of physical education & Sports.

References:

1. www.shivajiedusocamt.org
2. www. Dissertation Abstract/Sports library.
3. www.sportsdefinition.com.
4. Barrow H.M. (1983) Man and movement: principles of physical education, Third Edition, Lea & Fibiger, Philadelphia.
5. Clark David and Clark Harrison (1970). Research Process in Physical Education and health, New Jersey Printing Hall, INC.
6. Clark Harrison H, (1969) Application of Measurement to Health Physical Education. America Printing Hall, INC.
7. Annual Report, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krushi Vidyapeeth, Akola.
8. Annual Report, Shri Shivaji Education Society, Amravati
9. Annual Report, Sant Gadgebaba Amravati University, Amravati
10. Annual Report, Rashtrasant Tukadoji Maharaj Nagpur University, Nagpur